

OLS Organizing proposed framework For financial year 2023/24 (version 1)

Research on open

Community-based analyses to inform activities and interventions to increase the adoption of open science principles

Enabling the adoption of open science principles in local communities

Open incubator

Hands-on support to empower a next generation of open leaders in science

Open Science Training

Online mentoring and training programmes to enable individuals and teams worldwide to learn about and adopt open science practices

Open Science Training

Online mentoring and training programmes for individuals and teams worldwide to learn about and adopt open research practices.

Current work streams:

- Open Seeds
- NASA TOPS

What makes us different?

- Curriculum development & pedagogical expertise specifically in teaching researchers
- Programmes built with a global community of experienced community builders and open practitioners

Research on Open

Community-based, landscape and longitudinal analyses to inform activities and interventions for widening participation in research.

Current work streams:

- Impact research (supported by the Wellcome Trust)
- Turing Skills Policy Award

What makes us different?

- Researchers with demonstrated track record in researching and influencing open
- Inclusivity & equity-centred approach to research: train and incubate independent research leaders, compensate contributors, foster collaborations

Open Incubator

Hands-on support to empower the next generation of open leaders in research.

Current work streams:

- Fellowship programmes
- Facilitators training
- Catalyst
- Fiscal hosting (to come)
- Grant writing training (to come)

What makes us different?

- High touch: we work with leaders individually on their personal development